

A Cross-National Empirical Analysis of the Contribution of Fertility, Life Expectancy and Net Migration in Driving Contemporary and Future Population Ageing

Charmaine Savia Siqueira Lobo ¹, Savio da Piedade Falleiro ²

1 *Fr. Agnel College of Arts & Commerce, Pilar, Goa, 403203, India*

2 *Rosary College of Commerce and Arts, Navelim, Goa, 403707, India*

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Abstract

Population ageing is an unprecedented phenomenon witnessed by nations globally. Given contradictory findings in the literature regarding the major drivers behind this phenomenon, this study presents a robust cross-national empirical analysis of the contributions of fertility, life expectancy, and net migration to driving contemporary and future population ageing. The study addresses endogeneity and serial correlation by employing dynamic cointegrating regressions, specifically Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), based on data extracted from the United Nations Population Division for 72 nations spanning two periods: 1960-2020 and 2020-2050. The results indicate that nations in advanced ageing transitions, primarily developed nations, experienced comparatively lower fertility rates and higher life expectancy rates than those in early stages, with fluctuations observed in net migration. A statistically significant long-run dynamic cointegrating relationship is found among the three major drivers and population ageing. Declining fertility has been the primary driver of global population ageing from 1960 to 2020, followed by increasing life expectancy and, lastly, net migration. These results remain robust across the four sub-panels of nations based on age-transition categories. Projections suggest that population ageing will persist as a reality. However, regression estimates indicate that life expectancy will surpass fertility to become the primary driver of ageing in the future. The study raises doubt about the rejuvenating role of migration as a solution to population ageing and underscores the importance of further research in this area.

Keywords

ageing transitions, cointegration analysis, cross-sectional dependence, demographic drivers, demographic projections, DOLS, FMOLS, population ageing

JEL codes: C23, F22, J11, J13

Introduction

Population ageing entails an increase in the proportion of individuals aged 65 years and over. According to projections from the United Nations (UN), the global share of the elderly is expected to quadruple from 595 million to 2 billion between the years 2000 and 2050 (UN 2022). In 2018, the global share of older adults surpassed that of children under five years, marking an unprecedented and unparalleled historical milestone. This phenomenon is predicted to accelerate as the twenty-first century advances.

Economics and Demography are not separate entities; rather, they are closely intertwined. There exists a strong interconnection between the two fields. Economic factors influence demographic shifts, while demographic changes, in turn, impact economic dynamics. From one angle, economic conditions such as growth, government spending, social welfare policies, and market forces are affected by demographic shifts, such as changes in the proportion of older adults or fluctuations in the working-age population (Bagautdinova et al. 2014). Conversely, demographic trends, including fertility rates, mortality rates, and migration patterns, collectively referred to as the demographic drivers of an ageing population by Poston and Bouvier (2010), are influenced by economic conditions, thereby influencing a nation's population size and distribution (Roos & Zaun 2016).

However, ongoing discussions have emerged, as outlined in the literature, regarding how to measure the contributions of these demographic drivers towards population ageing, particularly concerning which among the three has been most influential for the current pace of global population ageing. Some studies strongly contend that population ageing has been caused by declines in fertility, primarily advocated by employing stable population models (Keyfitz 1975; Regional model... 1983; Weil 1997; Bengtsson & Scott 2011; Lee 2011). A few others suggest that population ageing is primarily driven by declining mortality (Bourgeois-Pichat 1978; Preston et al. 1989; Caselli & Vallin 1990; Horiuchi 1991; Horiuchi & Wilmoth 1998; Preston & Stokes 2012). However, they have been criticized for ignoring or keeping constant key demographic variables (Lee & Zhou 2017). Additionally, the significance of migration in shaping population ageing has received inconsistent findings (Alho 2008; Paterno 2011; UN 2017).

Through an economic lens, this study aims to analyze the contribution of fertility, life expectancy, and net migration in driving contemporary and future population ageing. A significant improvement of this study over prior literature lies in employing life expectancy at birth as a proxy for mortality rates. This choice is made because a population's life expectancy encompasses mortality trends spanning every stage of life, prevalent among infants, youth, adults, including older adults (Miladinov 2020). Similarly, Klenk et al. (2007) advocate that, compared to mortality levels, life expectancy represents an increasingly understandable and practical aggregate measure of mortality.

The study contributes to the debate in the literature concerning the conflicting views over the supremacy of the drivers of population ageing. Firstly, it systematically showcases the trends in the demographic drivers spanning six decades (1960-2020). Secondly, it presents an improvement over existing studies by testing the existential significance of a long-run cointegrating relation linking population ageing and the three prominent demographic variables. This is achieved by employing robust and dynamic cointegrating regression analysis, namely Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), in addition to Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), as opposed to stable population models and closed economies. Thirdly, the contribution of the three major forces in the greying of nations is intensely stud-

ied on a global panel of 72 nations spanning six decades (1960-2020), besides dissecting the panel into four sub-panels of nations based on the stages of their ageing transition. Fourthly, based on data projected by the UN (2022) up to the year 2050, this study analyzes which of the three drivers will reign superior in contributing to future ageing.

Literature review and research questions

Declines in fertility as the major contributor to population ageing

Over generations, researchers have gained insights into the mechanisms determining age structure primarily by using stable population models (Keyfitz 1975; Lee 2011). These models keep age-specific birth and death rates constant over a sizable amount of time, eventually resulting in the stabilization of the population's age structure. As an illustration, the stable population simulations by Coale et al. (Regional model... 1983) graphically represent the old-age dependence ratio utilizing isoquants across different fertility and life expectancy rates. Employing empirical life tables recorded in developed societies over 150 years corresponding to Northern, Southern, Eastern, and Western Europe, they demonstrate that the ageing of the stable population is significantly more pronounced due to declining fertility compared to decreasing mortality.

Bengtsson and Scott (2011) updated the calculations of Coale et al. (Regional model... 1983) utilizing one-year age-group data spanning the twentieth century. They discovered that with consistent fertility, the proportion of individuals aged 65 and older in Sweden would have been 8% in 2000, mirroring the rate from 1900, signifying minimal alteration over this interval. In both cases (Regional model... 1983; Bengtsson & Scott 2011), the argument proceeds that substantial advancements in mortality exert a relatively modest influence on population ageing. Similarly, Weil (1997) offered insights into four stable populations of the US, keeping 1989 as a point of comparison. The relative importance of changes in births and deaths was evaluated by examining each component separately. They concluded that shifts in fertility accounted for roughly two-thirds of the rise in the share of older adults.

Unfortunately, as pointed out by Lee and Zhou (2017), the drawback of using stable population simulations lies in the fact that the interval between one stable population and another is not accounted for by such models. Given that both developed and developing nations are presently in a transitional stage, such stable population models become only marginally relevant. Véron (2002) rightly advocated that the essential stability requirement necessitates that a group of age-specific growth rates remain uniform across different age categories. However, this condition is fulfilled by only a limited number of present-day populations, a fact that prompted Keyfitz (1975) to question the applicability of stable population models in comprehending the dynamics of real-world population ageing.

In a relatively recent article, Lee and Zhou (2017) conducted analytical simulations for India and More Developed Countries (MDCs), assuming closed economies by ignoring migration for simplicity's sake. They revealed that fertility change has overwhelmingly influenced population ageing observed in the past century. Furthermore, using UN population projections to analyze the factors driving alterations in demographics from 2015 to 2100, they emphasized that as the fertility rate stabilizes and life expectancy persists in its upward trajectory in the future, the impact of alterations in mortality will gain greater prominence.

However, while critically appraising the work of Lee and Zhou (2017), Murphy (2021) warned that the results of analytical simulations, as adopted by the former, hinge on the

chosen base year and population momentum. He commented that though the primary findings remain consistent, specifically, that population ageing is primarily driven by declining fertility, he underscored that the role of enhanced survival has become increasingly significant in contemporary times. We thus turn to the literature purporting population ageing to declining mortality, i.e., rising life expectancy.

Declines in mortality as the major contributor to population ageing

With enhancements in survival particularly concentrated among the elderly and very old age groups in decades subsequent to World War II, accompanied by a form of ageing “at the apex” (Bourgeois-Pichat 1978) or “from the top” (Preston et al. 1989), certain “revisionist” scholars have raised objections to the notion that fertility consistently remains the primary driver behind population ageing. A series of scholarly works surfaced (Preston et al. 1989; Caselli & Vallin 1990; Horiuchi 1991; Horiuchi & Wilmoth 1998), with the most recent being that of Preston and Stokes (2012), contending that the ongoing process of population ageing in recent times is predominantly attributable to decreasing mortality rates. This line of research has produced sophisticated models for understanding shifts in the population’s average age and conducted associated analysis aimed at elucidating transitional changes. For instance, based on information gathered from the UN for industrialized and developing nations, Preston and Stokes (2012) analyzed the causes of ageing between 2005 and 2010. Utilizing an accounting model wherein age-specific growth rates are delineated as the summation of births, survival, and migration, they demonstrated the most significant contributor to ageing among industrialized and less developed countries to be the enormous increases in survival.

Utilizing data from the Human Mortality Database spanning from 1850 onwards among 11 European nations, Murphy (2017) estimated the influence of mortality, fertility, and migration on European population ageing. He decomposed ageing into mortality, births, and net migration. He observed that the gradual rise in mortality outweighs the erratic fertility element. He pointed out that net migration only negligibly and temporarily impacted ageing populations. The findings supported the hypothesis that mortality supplanted fertility as the primary cause of ageing in wealthy nations, and low- and middle-income ones will subsequently pursue this trend.

Extracting data from the Human Mortality Database encompassing Oceania, North America, and Europe, De Santis and Salinari (2023) uncovered a cointegrating relationship between the age structures of population under research and its stationary population equivalent. They demonstrated that the majority of the shifts witnessed in the shares of youth, middle-aged, and older populace among these countries is attributable exclusively to changes in longevity.

The importance of migration in population ageing

The influence of migration in moulding and combating the greying of nations showcases mixed findings. A report published by the UN (2017) found that though immigration significantly rejuvenates the demographics of the recipient nations, it cannot stop or counteract the long-run trend of population ageing. In developed areas, population ageing is anticipated to be slowed through migration. In industrialized regions, the average age in 2050 is expected to be 1.7 years higher under the proposed forecast with no net migration, versus the

alternative scenario with migration sustaining at present rates. Alho (2008) analyzed the migration-fertility trade-off by utilizing a straightforward and stable open-population model, wherein cohort net migration is directly correlated with births. The impact of the age-specific pattern of net migration is encapsulated in a migration-survivor function, utilizing data from 17 European nations. The results illustrate that some countries already exhibit a migration level conducive to population stability, while for nations experiencing population decline, migration remains a viable avenue for alleviating the overall ageing of the population.

In an attempt to study whether immigration is the solution to population ageing in 103 provinces in Italy between 2001-2002 and 2008-2009, Paterno (2011) suggested that the influence of inflows of foreigners in slowing the rise in the average age is constrained and falls short of what is achieved through fertility. He observed that internal migration effectively countered the rise in the mean age of the population and concluded that immigration represents just one solution, which, while potentially beneficial in certain instances, is not inherently adequate.

Research questions and Hypotheses

The review above highlights conflicting views that stimulate two major research questions serving as a guide in analyzing the contribution of the three drivers of population ageing:

1. Which of the three drivers has reigned superior in driving the global greying of nations?
2. What will be the driving force channeling global population ageing in the future?

To aid our analysis further of the first research question, we test two hypotheses (H1 and H2):

H1) There is a significant dynamic long-run relation between population ageing and its three drivers.

H2) The prominent driving force of population ageing is consistent across ageing transition nation categories.

Methods

Classification of nations based on ageing transition stages

According to a report by the UN, a country is termed “Super-Aged” when the proportion aged 65 and older exceeds 20%, “Aged” if this percentage is 14% or over, and “Ageing” if this proportion is above 7% (World Bank 2021). Countries with an older population below 7% have been classified as “Potentially Ageing” nations for purpose of comparison. Given that population ageing is a phenomenon taking place over a period of time, wherein nations can transition from one ageing category to the other, we group nations into four transition categories namely: (i) Aged Nations to Super Aged Nations, (ii) Ageing Nations to Aged Nations (iii) Potentially Ageing Nations to Ageing Nations and (iv) Potentially Ageing nations. The former two categories are designated as nations being in the “Advanced stages” of the ageing transition, while the latter two are referred to as nations in the “Initial stages” of the ageing transition. The number of nations in the advanced ageing transition stages, especially those that have transitioned from Aged to Super Aged Nations, are relatively fewer in comparison to the vast majority at the initial transition stages. Hence, the choice of nations has been accordingly made, in order to derive a panel dataset representative of the “World”, comprising

a total of 72 nations, that are further sub-divided into four sub-panels (based on the ageing transition stages), each sub-panel comprising of 18 nations.

The purpose of undertaking such a detailed methodology in sample selection was to obtain a “Balanced Panel with four groups”, having an equal number of observations, and that is balanced in terms of “Temporal Balance” and “Cross-Sectional Balance”. Such a panel dataset with equal-sized sub-panels offers several advantages for statistical analysis. Namely, it facilitates meaningful comparisons across groups since each group is equally represented, yields highly robust and reliable results, prevents biases that arise from uneven sample sizes by ensuring that each group contributes proportionately to the overall analysis, and finally, balancing both time and cross-sectional dimensions augments the inferential power of the dataset by providing more informative insights into trends, relationships, and interactions. The list of nations in each category is detailed in Table 1. It’s important to note that all nations in the advanced stages of the ageing transition are developed nations, except for Barbados and Uruguay, while all nations in the initial stages of the transition are developing economies, except for Israel.

Table 1. Nation Classification based on the Stage of their Ageing Transition

Advanced Transition Stages	Nations
Aged Nations to Super Aged Nations	Bulgaria, Estonia, Serbia, Germany, Japan, Croatia, Finland, Italy, France, Lithuania, Hungary, Latvia, Czechia, Portugal, Slovenia, Greece, Sweden, Denmark
Ageing Nations to Aged Nations	Albania, Poland, Korea Republic, United Kingdom, Australia, Norway, Barbados, Belarus, North Macedonia, Canada, Ukraine, Romania, Iceland, New Zealand, Switzerland, United States, Uruguay, Russian Federation
Initial Transition Stages	Nations
Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	Armenia, Bahamas, Costa Rica, Peru, Brazil, Chile, Türkiye, China, Mexico, Colombia, Ecuador, Israel, Jamaica, Mauritius, Morocco, Panama, Thailand, Malaysia
Potentially Ageing Nations	Azerbaijan, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Belize, Bolivia, Botswana, Egypt, Guatemala, India, Indonesia, Jordan, Mongolia, Nepal, Nigeria, Paraguay, Philippines, Qatar, Uganda

Source: (UN 2022). *Note:* Nations are classified on the basis of the percentage share of their elderly in the population.

Data procurement

A dataset comprising the above mentioned 72 countries has been extracted from the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the UN Population Division, 2022, comprising:

- i. Population Ageing (POPAG): Proportion of people 65 years and older in the population.
- ii. Total Fertility Rate (FERT): Average number of live births a woman is expected to have at the conclusion of her reproductive years, as determined by the age-specific fertility rates prevalent in the specified year.

- iii. Life Expectancy at Birth (LEXP): Average number of years a newborn would anticipate living subject to the era's prevailing age-specific death rates.
- iv. Net Migration Rate (MIGR): Net total of migrants during a specific period, obtained by subtracting the total emigrants, including citizens and noncitizens, from total immigrants.

Analysis procedure

Cointegration analysis using panel data constitutes a four-step procedure testing for: (i) Cross-Sectional Dependence, (ii) Unit Root, (iii) Cointegration, and (iv) Computation of long run relations. Prior to applying unit root tests, it is crucial to scrutinize whether the data exhibits cross-sectional dependence or independence. Cross-sectional dependence denotes the existence of interdependence or correlation among observations within the cross-section of a dataset. To assess this, we utilize the Cross-sectional Dependence (CD) test developed by MH Pesaran (2021). The next step involves analysing the stationarity of the series, as non-stationary data provide erroneous estimates. Nevertheless, traditional unit root tests often yield weak results with low power in the presence of cross-sectional dependence among series. Consequently, we adopt a second-generation unit root test introduced by Pesaran (2007), known as the Cross-sectionally Augmented Im, Pesaran and Shin (CIPS) panel unit root test. Upon investigating that every variable is integrated of order one, we run Pedroni's Cointegration test (Pedroni 1999, 2004) that accommodates deterministic trends and is commonly employed for models involving cross-sectional dependency. Following is the panel cointegration empirical specification:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \delta_i t + \beta_1 X_{1,i,t} + \beta_2 X_{2,i,t} + \dots + \beta_n X_{n,i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

In the given context, $Y_{i,t}$ denotes the dependent variable, while $X_{n,i,t}$ represents independent variables, where n signifies the count of exogenous variables incorporated into the long-run estimation. The term $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ stands for the estimated residual, capturing deviations from the long-run equilibrium relationship. The slope coefficient is denoted by β and the parameters α_i and δ_i account for potential country-specific effects and deterministic trend effects, respectively. The observational units are indexed as $i = 1, \dots, N$, and periods as $t = 1, \dots, T$.

Pedroni (1999) proposed both panel and group tests to assess the null hypothesis of no cointegration in heterogeneous panels. Panel tests, utilizing the within-dimension approach, consist of four statistics: panel v -statistic, panel rho-statistic, panel PP-statistic, and panel ADF-statistic (also referred to as the panel cointegration statistics). These test the hypothesis of no cointegration across the entire panel.

Conversely, group tests, based on the between-dimension approach, involve three statistics: group rho-statistic, group PP-statistic, and group ADF-statistic (i.e., group mean panel cointegration statistics). These examine the null hypothesis of no cointegration within each group of the panel.

The determination of cointegration's existence in at least one group depends on the significance of the group statistics. The decision rule for each type of statistic is independent. Typically, if any of the group or panel statistics are statistically significant at a chosen significance level, it suggests evidence of cointegration.

Given the presence of cointegration among the variables, the estimation of the long-term equilibrium relation is essential. However, Pedroni (2004) argues that when used

on a cointegrated panel, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator becomes biased and unstable. Its distribution relies on nuisance parameters, which introduce undesired instances of endogeneity and serial correlation into the regression model, impacting its integrity.

To address these issues, the Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) devised by McCoskey and Kao (1998), along with Phillips and Moon (1999), and the Dynamic OLS (DOLS) designed by McCoskey and Kao (1998) and Kao and Chiang (2001), are employed. A thorough description of these methods can be found in Kao and Chiang (2001) and McCoskey and Kao (1998).

The FMOLS estimator, $\hat{\beta}_{FM}$ relies on a cointegrated framework for a panel of $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$, shown in Equation 1 and allows for the incorporation of endogeneity and serial correlation adjustments compared to the OLS estimator. The Dynamic OLS (DOLS) estimator ($\hat{\beta}_{DOLS}$) also corrects for serial correlation and endogeneity problems. However, the panel DOLS estimator outperforms the OLS and FMOLS estimators regarding sample attributes (Kao & Chiang 2001) as it includes leads and lags of the differences of the independent variables to surpass endogeneity and serial correlation issues. $\hat{\beta}_{DOLS}$ is derived from Equation (2), where c_{ij} is the estimated value of the lag or lead of the first differenced independent variables. The selection of the number of lags and leads is automatically done using EViews software (version 12) based on Schwarz criteria.

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta x_{it} + \sum_{j=q_1}^{j=q_2} c_{ij} \Delta x_{i,t-j} + v_{it}. \quad (2)$$

Given the assumption of differences in data quality and heterogeneity across different countries used in the analysis, especially those at the initial stages of the ageing transition, our study mitigates this phenomenon by employing suitable methodology, as discussed above, that allows for robust heterogeneous dynamics and heterogeneous cointegrating vectors (Pedroni 2001).

Results and Discussion

Global trends of population ageing and its demographic drivers

Figure 1 illustrates the proportion of older adults in the total population (POPAG) averaged across nations belonging to various stages of their ageing transition over six decades, from 1960 to 2020. The trend shows a rise in population ageing globally as well as across different nation categories. Specifically, nations that transitioned from being Aged to Super Aged show the highest increase, with the proportion of older adults rising from 8.84% in 1960 to 21.6% in 2020. Additionally, nations at the initial stages of the transition are also experiencing an upward trend in their elderly population.

Figure 2 illustrates the average global fertility rate (FERT) over six decades, from 1960 to 2020. The trend shows a decline in the average global fertility rate from approximately 4.6 live births per woman in 1960 to about 1.87 in 2020.

Specifically, the analysis reveals that Aged nations transitioning to Super Aged nations had the lowest fertility rate in 1960, around 2.5 live births per woman, which declined to about 1.57 live births per woman in 2020, showing the smallest decline

of around 0.93 live births across the six decades. Ageing nations transitioning to Aged nations also had relatively low fertility rates in the 1960s, around 3.44 live births per woman, compared to nations in the initial stages of their ageing transition. The sharpest decline in fertility rates over the six-decade period was experienced by nations transitioning from Potentially Ageing to Ageing, with a decrease of around 4.03 live births per woman, from 5.81 in 1960 to 1.78 in 2020. This was closely followed by a decline of 3.97 live births per woman among the Potentially Ageing nations, from 6.59 in 1960 to 2.62 in 2020.

Figure 1. Population Ageing (POPAG)1960-2020. *Source:* (UN 2022)

Figure 3 illustrates the average worldwide life expectancy (LEXP) over six decades, from 1960 to 2020. The trend shows a consistent rise in average life expectancy globally, from approximately 60 years in 1960 to about 77 years in 2020.

Examining each nation category separately, a similar trend of increasing life expectancy is observed across the six decades. For nations in advanced stages of transition, such as those transitioning from Aged to Super Aged, and Ageing to Aged, there is a significant increase in life expectancy. For instance, the average life expectancy among Aged to Super Aged

Figure 2. Fertility Rate (FERT) 1960-2020. *Source:* (UN 2022)

nations grew from around 67 years in 1960 to approximately 79 years in 2020, while Ageing to Aged countries saw an increase from 66 years in 1960 to nearly 80 years in 2020, representing a 12 to 14-year increase.

Additionally, while Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations and Potentially Ageing nations had lower life expectancies, they also experienced rising trends. Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations saw the sharpest rise in average life expectancy, increasing by around 20 years from approximately 57 years in 1960 to about 77 years in 2020. Potentially Ageing nations witnessed an average increase of 11 years across the six decades, from around 49 years in 1960 to approximately 60 years in 2020. Thus, life expectancy is increasing in advanced and developing nations.

Figure 4 showcases the fluctuations in the average net migration rate (MIGR) experienced across the six-decade period. The Aged to Super Aged nations have continuously experienced positive and negative phases in their average net migration rate right from 1960 to 2020, a positive rate indicating a greater influx of immigrants, while a negative rate highlighting a larger outflow of emigrants from these nations. However, though the Ageing to Aged nations initially witnessed variations in their average net migration rate, post 1999 a continuous positive trend in the same was witnessed. On the other hand, the Poten-

tially Ageing to Ageing nations demonstrated a continuous negative trend right up to the year 2005, following which their average net migration rate turned positive. Interestingly, the Potentially Ageing nations witnessed a relatively positive average net migration rate, except for recent years. Thus, globally the average net migration rate has been relatively positive spanning six-decades.

Figure 3. Life Expectancy (LEXP) 1960-2020. *Source:* (UN 2022)

The long-term relation between demographic drivers and population ageing: Testing the cross-national empirical model

In this section we seek to answer the first research question: Which of the three drivers has reigned superior in driving the global greying of nations? We begin by testing our first hypothesis (H1): A statistically significant dynamic long-run relation exists between the three drivers and population ageing, as opposed to stable population models. We do so by testing for cointegration. Equation (3) specifies the relation between population ageing and its drivers:

$$POPAG_{i,t} = f(FERT_{i,t}, LEXP_{i,t}, MIGR_{i,t}). \quad (3)$$

Figure 4. Net Migration Rate (MIGR) 1960-2020. *Source:* (UN 2022)

Equation (3) is extended to Equation (4), creating a model that will act as the empirical foundation for the models employed in this section using panel cointegration and dynamic panel data procedures.

$$POPAG_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FERT_{i,t} + \beta_2 LEXP_{i,t} + \beta_3 MIGR_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}. \tag{4}$$

Cross-sectional dependence

Before conducting unit root tests, we initially examine whether the sample data exhibits cross-sectional dependence or independence. To achieve this, we utilize the Cross-sectional dependence (CD) test proposed by Pesaran (2021). The results of the CD test are presented in Table 2. The findings indicate a robust rejection of the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence at the 1% significance level for all variables (POPAG, FERT, LEXP, and MIGR) within the global (world) sample and across individual categories of nations in various stages of their ageing transition. It is established that all variables exhibit cross-sectional dependence, signifying the existence of interdependence or correlation among observations within cross-sections.

Table 2. Pesaran's Cross-sectional Dependence (CD) test

	POPAG	FERT	LEXP	MIGR
World	251.08***	317.17***	306.57***	14.70***
Aged to Super Aged Nations	91.82***	66.26***	78.00***	11.92***
Ageing to Aged Nations	89.41***	76.40***	70.23***	8.57***
Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	82.30***	92.36***	88.51***	7.32***
Potentially Ageing Nations	12.46***	88.39***	68.48***	7.13***

Source: authors' calculations. *** Significant at the 1% level.

Panel unit root tests

In light of the identified cross-sectional dependence, traditional unit root tests exhibit limited effectiveness with low power. Consequently, we employ a second-generation panel unit root test that accounts for cross-sectional dependence, developed by Pesaran (2007): the Cross-sectionally Augmented Im, Pesaran and Shin (CIPS) panel unit root test. This test is based on the null hypothesis of non-stationarity, implying the existence of a unit root. The outcomes of the Pesaran CIPS unit root test are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Cross-sectionally augmented Im, Pesaran and Shin (CIPS) Panel Unit Root test

	Variables at level			
	POPAG	FERT	LEXP	MIGR
World	-2.048	-2.50	-2.392	-2.202
Aged to Super Aged Nations	-2.337	-2.528	-2.513	-2.481
Ageing to Aged Nations	-2.232	-2.601	-2.263	-2.271
Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	-1.336	-2.570	-2.507	-2.437
Potentially Ageing Nations	-2.090	-2.275	-2.462	-2.774
	Variables at first difference			
	ΔPOPAG	ΔFERT	ΔLEXP	ΔMIGR
World	-2.665***	-3.927***	-4.438***	-3.202***
Aged to Super Aged Nations	-2.871***	-4.383***	-3.813***	-4.450***
Ageing to Aged Nations	-2.897***	-4.769***	-5.845***	-4.303***
Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	-2.977***	-4.138***	-4.505***	-4.700***
Potentially Ageing Nations	-2.925***	-3.561***	-3.907***	-4.655***

Source: authors' calculations. *** Significant at the 1% level. Note: The critical values (constant and trend) of CIPS Pesaran (2007) test based on 2 lags for the World sample of 72 nations at 1% and 5% are -2.65 and -2.57; while that for the individual nation categories comprising 18 nations each at 1% and 5% are -2.85 and -2.7

The results from Table 3 indicate that, for all variables, the null hypothesis of non-stationarity cannot be rejected at the 5% significance level when considering the level data. However, when examining the first differences, the null hypothesis of non-stationarity is rejected at the 1% significance level for all variables. The CIPS tests are conducted with constant and

trend terms, incorporating two lags. Consequently, these outcomes suggest that all variables possess a unit root at their respective levels, indicating non-stationarity, but they exhibit stationarity at first differences. Therefore, it can be concluded that all variables are integrated of order I(1), meaning they are stationary in first differences. Hence, it is deduced that all variables are integrated of order I(1). These findings imply the potential existence of cointegration among the variables POPAG, FERT, LEXP, and MIGR, which necessitates further testing.

Panel cointegration test

The Pedroni test (Pedroni 1999) is used to confirm the third estimating phase, which tests for the presence of a cointegrating relation between population ageing and the demographic drivers. Testing the null hypothesis of no cointegration, the panel tests comprise four statistics, along with their weighted statistics, summing up to eight, while the group tests include three.

Table 4 presents the results of the panel cointegration test conducted for both the World and each ageing-transition nation category. The test examined the null hypothesis that cointegration does not exist between the demographic drivers and population ageing.

Table 4. Heterogenous Pedroni Cointegration test.

Test Statistic	World	Aged to Super Aged Nations	Ageing to Aged Nations	Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	Potentially Ageing Nations
Panel v-Statistic	-0.676 (0.751)	-0.337 (0.632)	-0.456 (0.676)	-0.389 (0.642)	-2.081 (0.981)
Panel rho-Statistic	-9.699 (0.000)***	-8.765 (0.000)***	-4.584 (0.000)***	-6.221 (0.000)***	-5.598 (0.000)***
Panel PP-Statistic	-13.632 (0.000)***	-10.995 (0.000)***	-7.301 (0.000)***	-8.843 (0.000)***	-7.873 (0.000)***
Panel ADF-Statistic	1.278 (0.899)	-2.952 (0.002)***	3.808 (0.999)	-3.783 (0.000)***	2.369 (0.991)
Panel v-Weighted Statistic	-0.873 (0.809)	-0.287 (0.613)	0.215 (0.415)	0.210 (0.412)	-2.723 (0.997)
Panel rho- Weighted Statistic	-3.874 (0.000)***	-9.116 (0.000)***	-3.988 (0.000)***	-4.675 (0.000)***	-5.407 (0.000)***
Panel PP-Weighted Statistic	-6.660 (0.000)***	-11.435 (0.000)***	-5.758 (0.000)***	-6.243 (0.000)***	-8.409 (0.000)***
Panel ADF-Weighted Statistic	3.302 (0.999)	-3.851 (0.000)***	2.733 (0.997)	-3.962 (0.000)***	3.239 (0.999)
Group rho-Statistic	-1.718 (0.043)**	-7.999 (0.000)***	-3.328 (0.000)***	-4.631 (0.000)***	-4.973 (0.000)***

Test Statistic	World	Aged to Super Aged Nations	Ageing to Aged Nations	Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations	Potentially Ageing Nations
Group PP-Statistic	-2.102 (0.018)**	-10.367 (0.000)***	-3.884 (0.000)***	-4.734 (0.000)***	-7.165 (0.000)***
Group ADF-Statistic	10.501 (1.000)	-0.649 (0.258)	7.049 (1.000)	6.129 (1.000)	4.958 (1.000)

Source: authors' calculations. *** Significant at the 1% level, ** Significant at the 5% level, * Significant at the 10% level. Optimal lag length designated based on the Schwarz Information Criterion, p-value indicated in brackets

Among the eleven statistics, six were significant at the 1% level for the World, Ageing to Aged nations, and Potentially Ageing nation categories, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Similarly, eight statistics were significant for Aged to Super Aged and Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations. These findings indicate the presence of a statistically significant dynamic long-run cointegrating relationship between the demographic drivers and population ageing, consistent with the study conducted by De Santis and Salinari (2023).

Therefore, we accept hypothesis H1, which suggests the existence of a significant dynamic long-run cointegrating relationship.

To investigate which of the three drivers predominates in driving global greying, we need to estimate the long-run relationship. However, using ordinary least squares (OLS) on a cointegrated panel can lead to biased estimates. Hence, we employ the Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) and Dynamic OLS (DOLS) methods to address this issue.

Long-run cointegration estimation: FMOLS and DOLS

Table 5 presents the results of the Fully Modified OLS (FMOLS) and Dynamic OLS (DOLS) tests for the period 1960–2020, examining the long-run relationship between the demographic drivers (fertility, life expectancy, and net migration) and population ageing.

The results from both the FMOLS and DOLS tests indicate the presence of robust and significant long-run relationships between the independent variables (fertility, life expectancy, and net migration) and population ageing. Additionally, the Adjusted R-Squared values, which indicate the goodness of fit of the models, are relatively good across all models.

In the majority of cases, the coefficient signs and statistical significance reported by the Panel DOLS test align with those noted in the Panel FMOLS test. However, there are slight differences in the magnitude of the coefficients of the independent variables between the FMOLS and DOLS models. As a result, the DOLS estimates tend to yield higher adjusted R-Squared values compared to FMOLS estimates.

Overall, the results from both FMOLS and DOLS tests provide evidence of significant long-run relationships between the demographic drivers and population ageing, with the DOLS estimates offering slightly better goodness of fit in terms of adjusted R-Squared values.

At the global (World) level, comprising 72 nations, we analyze the results to answer our first research question regarding the primary driver contributing to global population ageing. With regard to fertility rate (given our prior trend analysis of declining fertility in Figure 1), the estimation results in Table 5 imply that a unit reduction in global fertility raises

the global proportion of elderly by 1.36% (1.05%) based on FMOLS (DOLS) estimations, thus being the primary driver contributing significantly to global population greying at the 1% level. Life expectancy at birth is found to be the second most influential driver at the 1% level, with a unit increase in life expectancy leading to around 0.19% (0.18%) increase in population ageing based on FMOLS (DOLS) estimates. Lastly, though the magnitude of the impact of net migration is relatively low compared to the other two drivers, nevertheless, a rise in net migration significantly lowers population ageing by 0.03% in the case of FMOLS and DOLS estimations respectively at the 1% and 5% level.

Table 5. Panel FMOLS and Panel DOLS results (1960-2020).

Panel FMOLS Results					Panel DOLS Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
World									
FERT	-1.355	0.054	-24.971	0.000***	FERT	-1.045	0.062	-16.832	0.000***
LEXP	0.193	0.003	73.569	0.000***	LEXP	0.183	0.003	72.780	0.000***
MIGR	-0.027	0.010	-2.598	0.009***	MIGR	-0.029	0.014	-2.008	0.045**
<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.47</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.68</i>				
Aged to Super Aged Nations									
FERT	-5.133	0.267	-19.191	0.000***	FERT	-4.989	0.324	-15.422	0.000***
LEXP	0.312	0.007	46.410	0.000***	LEXP	0.318	0.008	40.463	0.000***
MIGR	0.498	0.082	6.0352	0.000***	MIGR	0.080	0.041	-1.936	0.053*
<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.36</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.69</i>				
Ageing to Aged Nations									
FERT	-1.919	0.151	-12.684	0.000***	FERT	-1.991	0.154	-12.957	0.000***
LEXP	0.210	0.005	45.289	0.000***	LEXP	0.217	0.004	52.114	0.000***
MIGR	0.110	0.024	4.555	0.000***	MIGR	0.171	0.021	8.069	0.000***
<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.57</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.75</i>				
Potentially Ageing to Ageing Nations									
FERT	-0.534	0.051	-10.412	0.000***	FERT	-0.362	0.065	-5.553	0.000***
LEXP	0.109	0.003	40.063	0.000***	LEXP	0.107	0.003	41.018	0.000***
MIGR	-0.019	0.016	-1.205	0.228	MIGR	-0.012	0.017	-0.732	0.465
<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.49</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.62</i>				
Potentially Ageing Nations									
FERT	-0.080	0.037	-2.153	0.031**	FERT	-0.097	0.037	-2.610	0.009***
LEXP	0.017	0.008	2.084	0.037**	LEXP	0.025	0.009	2.594	0.009***
MIGR	0.004	0.003	1.370	0.171	MIGR	0.006	0.000	-1.973	0.048**
<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.69</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared: 0.83</i>				

Source: authors' calculations. *** Significant at the 1% level, ** Significant at the 5% level, * Significant at the 10% level. The Schwarz Information Criterion determines the number of lags and leads in the case of DOLS.

To gain deeper insights into the predominant driving force behind population ageing, we seek to test hypothesis H2, which posits that the primary driving force of population ageing remains consistent across ageing transition nation categories. Table 5 points out that in comparison to the magnitude of the coefficients of life expectancy and net migration, those of fertility are found to exert significantly the highest influence in driving population ageing across the six decades from 1960-2020 concerning both the FMOLS (DOLS) estimations for the Aged to Super Aged nations [-5.133 (-4.989)], Ageing to Aged nations [(-1.919 (-1.991)), Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations [-0.534 (-0.362)] and Potentially Ageing nations [-0.080 (-0.097)] in most cases at the 1% level of significance. The strongest impact of this force driving population ageing is witnessed among Aged to Super Aged nations, followed by the Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations, while fertility declines exerted the lowest impact among Potentially Ageing nations in tune with the findings of Bengtsson and Scott (2011); Regional model... (1983); Keyfitz (1975); Lee (2011); Lee and Zhou (2017) and Weil (1997). Societal trends such as delayed childbearing contribute to declining fertility rates, exacerbating the effects on population ageing. A decline in fertility rates contributes to a demographic imbalance characterized by a shrinking proportion of younger individuals relative to older age groups. As birth rates decrease, there are fewer young people entering the population to replace ageing cohorts, leading to an overall ageing population structure. Increasing urbanization, industrialization, economic development and educational attainment, often correlate with declining fertility due to changes in lifestyle, healthcare access, and family structures (Nargund 2009).

The second most influential driver of population ageing by the order of magnitude of the impact is rising life expectancy owing to significantly positive estimated FMOLS(DOLS) coefficients in most cases at the 1% level for the Aged to Super Aged [0.312 (0.318)], Ageing to Aged [(0.210 (0.217)), Potentially Ageing to Ageing [0.109 (0.107)] and Potentially Ageing nations [0.017 (0.025)]. The strongest impact exerted by rising life expectancy in driving population ageing is witnessed once again among the Aged to Super Aged nations. A rise in life expectancy alters the shape of the population pyramid, typically transforming it from a pyramid with a broad base (indicating high birth rates and high mortality rates at younger ages) to a more rectangular or even an inverted pyramid (indicating lower birth rates and longer lifespans). This shift reflects a larger proportion of older individuals relative to younger ones, thereby contributing to population ageing (Chen 2023).

An interesting finding regarding net migration is the mixed impact observed across nations at various stages of their ageing transition. Fluctuations in migratory trends contribute to this variability. However, net migration consistently had the lowest influence among all four sub-samples of nations at different transition stages, based on the coefficients of the FMOLS and DOLS estimations, although at varying significance levels.

For instance, while a global negative impact was noted, a similar effect was observed among Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations [-0.019 (-0.012)], albeit statistically insignificant. In contrast, among Potentially Ageing nations, net migration showed an insignificant positive impact on population ageing based on FMOLS estimations (0.004), while the results were significant based on the DOLS estimations (0.006) at the 5% level of significance.

Conversely, a rise in net migration exhibited a significantly positive impact on population ageing among the Aged to Super Aged [0.498 (0.080)] and Ageing to Aged nations [0.110 (0.171)], respectively.

Thus, H2 is supported by the finding that fertility has consistently been the primary driving force of population ageing across all four nation ageing transition categories. This suggests a consistent pattern of fertility's dominance as the major driver, followed by life expectancy. However, variations in the extent of fertility's influence are observed, with the highest impact noted among Aged to Super Aged nations.

While uniformity is observed in the signs of the estimated coefficients of fertility (negative) and life expectancy (positive) across the global sample and the sub-samples of nations at different ageing transition stages, the shifting signs of net migration across the sub-panels require further examination. This intriguing feature challenges the concept of the "Rejuvenating Role of Migration" (Harper 2016).

The positive coefficient sign of net migration implies a net influx of immigrants, suggesting potential demographic rejuvenation. Conversely, a negative coefficient sign indicates a net outflow of emigrants, potentially contributing to population ageing. The dynamic nature of migration patterns and their impact on population ageing warrant deeper investigation to understand the complex interplay between migration trends and demographic shifts.

We reference a report published by the Global Commission on International Migration (GCIM) in Geneva titled "Migration in an Interconnected World: New Directions for Action." According to this report, in 2005, there were nearly 200 million international migrants, with approximately 60% residing in developed countries and the remaining 40% in developing countries. The report also noted that almost one in every 10 persons living in developed countries was a migrant (GCIM 2005). Analyzing these findings within the context of our study, which revealed that developed regions are primarily those in the advanced stages of their ageing transition, sheds light on the reason for the change in coefficient signs of net migration. Developed nations typically have a higher proportion of elderly individuals in the total population, coupled with a relatively higher net migration rate. This suggests a positive direction of the relationship, resulting in a significantly positive sign for the net migration coefficients in Aged to Super Aged nations and Ageing to Aged nations in both FMOLS and DOLS estimations.

In contrast, nations at the initial stages of the ageing transition, typically identified as developing economies, often experience a higher rate of emigration among their population, leading to an increasing proportion of elderly individuals over the six decades, albeit at a slower pace. This explains the negative sign observed among Potentially Ageing to Ageing nations. However, this finding is not statistically significant ($p > 0.1; 0.5; 0.01$), underscoring the fact that the net migration rate is influenced by the immigration and emigration policies of the nations under study. As indicated in the aforementioned report, developing countries also serve as destination countries for 40% of international migrants. Many of the potentially ageing nations in our study do not have very stringent immigration policies and are recipients of immigrants, thus resulting in positive net migration rates. At the same time, they have been experiencing a rise in their elderly population over six decades, leading to a positive correlation between the two variables. This positive relationship has been adequately captured by the robust DOLS regression estimation, owing to the use of leads and lags, as opposed to the FMOLS estimation. Thus, the relatively higher rates of population ageing and net migration have resulted in a stronger influence experienced by the developed nations at the advanced stages of the ageing transition compared to their counterparts at the initial stages, in line with discussions on variations in the moderating and converging factors in the ageing of nations (Backman & Karlsson 2023).

Future scenario of the demographic drivers of population ageing

Based on the projections of the United Nations Population Division, World Population Prospects: 2022 Revision, Figures 5, 6, 7, and 8 depict global projections of the aforementioned demographic phenomena averaged across nations belonging to various stages of their ageing transition, spanning the ensuing three decades from 2020 to 2050.

Figure 5 illustrates a sharply rising global phenomenon of population ageing, with the proportion of elderly individuals in the total populace increasing from 13% in 2020 to 16.21% by 2030 and further to 22.43% by 2050. Projections indicate that this surging phenomenon will be experienced by all nation categories across different stages of their ageing transition. By 2050, this share will remain the highest among the nations that transitioned from Aged to Super Aged, reaching up to 30.25% on average. Following closely are the nations that transitioned from Ageing to Aged, projected to further transition to Super Aged nations by approximately the year 2029, with slight variations across nations. Their share of older adults, on average, is anticipated to reach 26.90% by 2050. The nations that transitioned from Potentially Ageing to Ageing are further projected to transition to Aged nations by 2032 and further to Super Aged nations by 2048. In a similar vein, Potentially Ageing nations are projected to transition to Ageing nations on average by the year 2033.

Figure 5. Population Ageing (POPAG) 2020-2050. Source: (UN 2022)

As in Figure 6, globally, it is expected that average fertility rates will fall from 1.88 live births per woman in 2020 to 1.79 in 2030 to 1.72 by 2050. This global trend of declining fertility corresponds to nations that are currently transitioning from Potentially Ageing to Ageing including Potentially Ageing nations, which are also projected to face fertility rate declines on an average from 1.80 live births per woman in 2020 to 1.67 by 2050 in the case of the former, and from 2.66 live births per woman in 2020 to 1.99 by 2050 among the latter. However, the Aged to Super Aged nations are projected to witness a rise in average fertility from 1.53 live births in 2020 to 1.57 by 2030, rising to 1.60 by 2050. Similarly, fertility is projected to rise from 1.47 live births in 2020 to 1.59 by 2050 among Ageing to Aged nations.

Figure 6. Fertility Rate (FERT) 2020-2050. *Source:* (UN 2022)

Life expectancy at birth (depicted in Figure 7) is projected to gradually increase from 2020 to 2050, both globally and across nation categories belonging to different ageing stages. The highest average life expectancy is anticipated for the nations currently undergoing the transition from Aged to Super Aged. For instance, the average years a newborn is expected to live in nations currently at this transition phase will be approximately 84.48 years by the year 2050. This is followed by those transitioning from Ageing to Aged (84.02 years), Potentially Ageing to Ageing (82.05 years), and Potentially Ageing nations (76.71 years).

Figure 7. Life Expectancy (LEXP) 2020-2050. *Source:* (UN 2022)

Figure 8 projects that most of the Aged to Super Aged nations and the Ageing to Aged nations (previously highlighted as developed nations) will experience an influx of immigrants, leading to projections of a positive net migration rate for most of the period from 2020 to 2050. In contrast, nations currently transitioning from Potentially Ageing to Ageing and the Potentially Ageing nations are expected to witness a negative net migration rate due to a larger outflow of emigrants from these nations.

Given the projections of continued population ageing in the future, the study aims to investigate the second research question: What will be the driving force channelling global population ageing in the future? Table 6 provides an overview of the FMOLS and DOLS findings for the entire sample of 72 nations taken together over the period 2020-2050, examining which demographic driver will primarily contribute to future population ageing.

The coefficients of fertility rate are significantly negative at the 1% level according to the FMOLS (DOLS) estimates $[-0.739 (-0.856)]$, implying that a reduction in fertility raises the proportion of older adults, thus significantly contributing to driving future population ageing. Fertility rates in many countries will have reached or be near replacement level, while in many others, they will gradually start to rise, thus further declines would exert diminishing effects on population ageing. However, examining the estimated coefficients of life

expectancy reveals that rising life expectancy at birth surpasses fertility rates to become the major driver of global future population ageing according to the FMOLS (DOLS) estimates [1.960 (2.079)]. This suggests that increasing population ageing significantly, owing to significant advancements in healthcare, nutrition, sanitation, and lifestyle factors, will outweigh reductions in fertility rate. Finally, an increase in net migration rate is also found to significantly positively influence population ageing in the future [0.269 (1.159)], and with a higher magnitude compared to the impact it exerted over the prior six decades. This presents a key contribution to the economic analysis of demographic drivers, as rising life expectancy (declining mortality rates) will outweigh reductions in fertility rate, thus becoming the leading driver responsible for the greying of nations in the coming decades.

Figure 8. Net Migration (MIGR) 2020-2050. *Source:* (UN 2022)

The analysis of the signs of the estimated coefficients of the drivers of future population ageing, being as expected and in line with prior findings for fertility and life expectancy, once again draws our attention to the positive coefficient of net migration. This contrasts with the negative coefficient found for the global sample for the period 1960-2020 in Table 5, reaffirming our argument and questioning the rejuvenating role of migration. This points towards an emerging phenomenon coined as “Elderly Migration”. Discussions surround-

ing migration have often been marred by “Ageism”, characterized by a predominant focus on pervasive presumptions that migrants are predominantly youthful adults. However, elderly individuals, who have been hitherto neglected, are also engaged in migration and developmental processes. This manifests in heterogeneous ways across various geographical settings (Bastia et al. 2022).

Table 6. Panel FMOLS results (2020-2050)

Panel FMOLS Results					Panel DOLS Results				
Vari- able	Coeffi- cient	Std Error	t-Sta- tistic	Prob.	Vari- able	Coeffi- cient	Std Error	t-Sta- tistic	Prob
World 2020-2050									
FERT	-0.739	0.207	-3.573	0.000***	FERT	-0.856	0.406	-2.109	0.035**
LEXP	1.960	0.038	52.114	0.000***	LEXP	2.079	0.054	38.343	0.000***
MIGR	0.269	0.035	7.711	0.000***	MIGR	1.159	0.091	12.648	0.000***
<i>Adjusted R-Squared:0.62</i>					<i>Adjusted R-Squared:0.88</i>				

Source: authors’ calculations. Significant at the 1% level, ** Significant at the 5% level. The Schwarz Information Criterion determines the number of lags and leads in the case of DOLS.

Our findings align with the remarkable contributions of a select few exceptional studies. For example, Zaiceva (2014) demonstrates that following a decline at the age of 30, there is a subsequent peak of migration among older individuals, particularly upon retirement, indicating return migration. She convincingly asserts that population ageing, advancements in healthcare facilities, and retirement provisions are precipitating an increase in elderly migration, including return retirement migration, along with the mobility of specialized workers such as healthcare and long-term care providers.

Notably, she observes that the demographic of elderly individuals (aged over 65) among international migrants constitutes a significant proportion, totaling approximately 26 million or 11.1%. This demographic is more pronounced in developed regions (13%) compared to developing regions (8%), with Europe and Oceania registering the highest percentages. While the majority of international migrants relocate from less to more developed nations, there is a notable presence of elderly migrants, with Canada, Australia, and New Zealand already exhibiting proportions nearing those of working-age migrants. These countries, alongside Switzerland, encompass regions with the highest proportions of migrants aged over 65 within the overall population, reflecting historical migration trends, prior influxes, and lower proportions of native elderly populations.

In another compelling article that demystifies three economic myths surrounding ageing, Murray and van Onselen (2019) assert that the notion of high immigration as a panacea for population ageing is fallacious. They argue that while low immigration can help stabilize the age structure and mitigate population decline, high immigration offers minimal long-term benefits beyond increasing the overall population size. This approach poses significant challenges for the future, particularly as ageing results from extended lifespans, and immigrants themselves age at the same rate as the native population. Furthermore, Bermingham’s seminal research (2001) suggests that while immigration may address population decline, it is not a solution for population ageing. In line with the assertions of Murray and van Onselen

(2019), Bermingham also contends that immigrants, like all mortals, undergo ageing processes. The sheer magnitude of immigrants required to counterbalance declines in the ratio of working-age populations to the elderly is prohibitively high, rendering annual figures untenably excessive for serious consideration.

Conclusion

This study aims to enhance methodologies aimed at discerning the relative significance of three pivotal drivers of contemporary and future population ageing: fertility rates, life expectancy, and net migration. As societies transition demographically, the dynamics among these ageing determinants undergo a transformative shift. Traditional paradigms, including the stable population model, experience varying degrees of diminishment in their explanatory and prognostic efficacy. Consequently, there arises a requisite for novel methodologies capable of elucidating not only the intrinsic interconnections among population ageing factors but also the stability of these associations, via robust and dynamic estimations.

In light of the fact that the ageing stages—Super Aged, Aged, and Ageing—are not water-tight compartments but rather represent phases of transition, across which nations evolve from one to another over several decades, the present study incorporates this aspect by classifying nations into ageing transition stages. Additionally, it defines a fourth category, the Potentially Ageing nations, in order to include several nations at the initial stages of the transition that have been excluded from analysis in prior studies. This inclusion serves as a means of comparison with nations at advanced ageing transition stages in the present study.

Considering the presumption of cross-national diversity and consequently variations in data quality, the robust methodology adopted addresses the same by enabling the examination of heterogeneous cointegrating vectors.

While global fertility has fallen, longevity rates have been soaring. Nations in advanced ageing transitions, primarily encompassing developed nations, have witnessed comparatively lower fertility and higher life expectancy rates than their counterparts in the early stages, with fluctuations in net migration being observed. A statistically significant long-run dynamic cointegrating relationship between the three major demographic variables and cross-national population ageing was identified in the global panel as well as in each of the four transition categories. Declining fertility was found to have reigned superior in significantly driving population ageing over the six decades (1960–2020) in the global panel, followed by life expectancy, and lastly net migration. Across the four categories of nations at different ageing transitions, the order of influence of the drivers was found to be the same, with declining fertility being the predominant driver.

Projections up to the year 2050 indicate that the sharply rising global phenomenon of population ageing will continue to be a reality in ensuing decades as nations progress further towards advanced stages of ageing transition. Nevertheless, although global fertility rates will fall in the future, nations in the advanced stages will start experiencing a rise in fertility along with an influx of immigrants leading to a positive net migration rate. However, life expectancy will continue to rise among all nations, and estimates indicate that the latter will surpass fertility rates to become the major driver of global population ageing in the future. Our findings are in tune with the predictive arguments set out by Horiuchi (1991) who stated that as life expectancies continue to rise globally, owing to declining mortality, its impacts become more pronounced with advancing age, while the decline

in fertility becomes constrained, signifying that the influence of earlier fertility decline is fully realized.

Given that the findings of the present study are based on a sample of 72 nations, future research can build on this limitation by comparing the results with larger panels and sub-panels of nations. The contradiction in the impact, especially the coefficient signs, of net migration on contemporary and future population ageing questions the rejuvenating role of migration and spurs the need for investigation into the rising phenomenon of “Elderly Migration”.

Areas for potential research could include cross-national empirical comparisons of the economic and non-economic factors influencing elderly migration and how they differ from factors influencing people at working age. Given that the elderly themselves are a heterogeneous group, analyzing differences in migratory inclinations within the elderly subset, such as among the “Young-Old”, “Old-Old”, and “Very-Old”, could provide further insights into this phenomenon. This is of immense necessity owing to the far-reaching implications it will have on the source and destination countries’ labor markets and welfare systems.

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Data Resources

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Information about the authors

- Charmaine Savia Siqueira Lobo – Masters of the Faculty of Economics, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Fr. Agnel College of Arts & Commerce, Pilar, affiliated to Goa Business School, Goa University, Goa, 403206, India. Email: charmaine@fragnelcollege.edu.in ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3010-4815>
- Savio da Piedade Falleiro – Doctor of Economics, Professor, Department of Economics, Rosary College of Commerce and Arts, Navelim, Goa, 403707, India. Email: saviofalleiro@gmail.com ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3010-4815>